

Director's Message

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In this edition of *The Mirror*, we mark the 25th anniversary of the discovery of Dark Energy with a number of contributions from the key people, and NOIRLab facilities, involved in its discovery and follow-ups. We are privileged to have their contributions and to share in their recollections of key events in the history of cosmology and astrophysics. Only in astronomy will one see a celebration of the 25th anniversary of the discovery of ... *we don't really know what!* Dark Energy drives the acceleration of the cosmic expansion and will play an increasingly dominant role in the future of the Universe on the largest scales. The nature of dark energy, however, is still poorly understood. How we got to this point in science is an interesting story that our guest authors share with us.

Behind this landmark scientific breakthrough is a story of decades of hard work, innovation, creativity, and perseverance. Many people over many years helped set the stage for this discovery, and much work was needed to bring it to fruition. This story is told in the pages of this issue, and the facilities and staff of NOIRLab's predecessor organizations feature prominently in the narrative.

There were many steps on the path to making supernova cosmology a reality. A key first requirement was a wide-field imaging capability powerful enough to allow large areas of the sky to be surveyed for supernovae. The survey needed large blocks of nights, only available through the survey/long-term proposal option offered by NOAO at the time. It required large-format linear detector arrays in cameras with large and well-corrected fields of view. The surveys needed to reach faint levels to allow access to SNe at interesting redshifts. While Type 1a SNe are luminous, they are faint when seen at cosmological distances.

The 4m telescopes at KPNO and CTIO were just the right tools for this work. The Mosaic camera at the prime focus of the Blanco 4m telescope was the engine for the supernova cosmology project of Schmidt et al. and the program by Perlmutter et al. Discovering faint SNe is not easy. In addition to the primary survey, one needs follow-on observations to detect transient objects. Sophisticated software is needed to find SNe amongst the light of their host galaxies. Image subtraction is the technique of choice – but quite a bit of software is needed to match the point-spread-functions and avoid thousands of false positives that would swamp true SNe transients.

Making sense of the SNe detections requires a deep familiarity with the spectra and lightcurves of the many varieties of supernovae. Type 1a SNe are not *standard candles*, rather they are *calibratable candles*, and one needs precise and dense sampling of

the lightcurves to perform the necessary calibrations. The correlation between the rate of decline and absolute magnitude was key to making Type 1a SNe useful for cosmology. All of this was made possible through the early development of *time-domain astrophysics*. Spectroscopy is the complement of time-domain imaging – it allows classification of the phenomena and was essential to bringing clarity to the Type 1a phenomenon. None of this is possible without a suitable communications infrastructure that alerts observers, and observatories, to candidate transients in time to allow follow-up observations before they fade beyond reach.

It is remarkable that much of the mission of NOIRLab in the 21st century is rooted in the discovery of Dark Energy and the techniques that made it possible in the last century. The Dark Energy Camera took up the challenge where the Mosaic cameras left off to survey a large fraction of the southern sky to faint levels with good time coverage. The GMOS spectrographs on Gemini North & South proved to be powerful tools for low-resolution SNe spectroscopy and classification.

The Rubin Observatory will take dark energy research to the next level with both a next-generation wide-field deep time-domain survey, plus an ambitious full southern-sky weak lensing survey. Sophisticated detection algorithms, real-time alerts, and a network of telescopes and instruments will enable the detection and characterization of thousands of SNe to be used as probes of the expansion history of the Universe. Exquisitely precise image-shape analysis will isolate the subtle large-scale weak lensing signal that will testify to the effects of Dark Energy on the growth of structure over cosmological time. Photometric redshifts will allow us to measure peaks in the power spectrum imprinted by baryonic acoustic oscillations. Decades of development have gone into building the telescope, the powerful camera, the software, the science platform, and the community of scientists needed to make this a reality.

NOIRLab and the community of users have created powerful event brokers (including ANTARES) and a network of follow-up capabilities linked by sophisticated software (AEON) to allow scientists to follow up on all manner of transients from Rubin's LSST. Gemini, SOAR, and other telescopes with powerful spectrographs will be the key astrophysics machines for Rubin follow-up.

As we reflect on 25 years of Dark Energy, we can look forward to another 25 years of discovery with Rubin, Gemini, and the 4m telescopes (and software!) playing key roles. Before the Rubin Observatory was "Rubin" or "LSST," it was the *Dark Matter Telescope*; it may well turn out to be the *Dark Energy Telescope*.